

Evolutionary Synthesis Center

Scientific Objectives, Structure and Implementation Plan

A report based upon two workshops:

*ESC Workshop I: NSF Headquarters, Arlington,
Virginia*

May 28 – June 1, 2001

*ESC Workshop II: Belmont Conference Center,
Elkridge, Maryland*

January 31 – February 3, 2002

Summary

Evolution has long served to unify the study of biology. Today, evolution has taken on an even greater role, as it serves to inform and direct data acquisition, analysis and interpretation across the life sciences. This transformation comes in part from an explosion of raw data, from sources as far ranging as whole genome sequences and phylogenetics to long-term behavior studies and functional morphology. Such data and metadata can only be interpreted using advanced mathematical and statistical approaches built on evolutionary concepts and depends on highly developed database management and analysis tools. Whether we seek to understand the emergence of new diseases, develop new more effective plant cultivars, or account for the content and organization of newly sequenced genomes, we are using a comparative, evolutionary-based approach.

As formerly disparate fields of biological research converge, evolutionary biology is providing the common language. Evolutionary biology is poised to serve as the focal point for the synthesis and interpretation of these massive and growing data sets. Even more compelling, it is the only field in the biological sciences capable of providing a unifying framework for fields as far ranging as rational drug design, developmental biology, cell biology, behavior, morphology, physiology, genetics, ecology, phylogenetics, and organismal biology. Evolution can, and should, play a similarly central role in addressing a suite of critical national concerns. For example, evolutionary biology has a pivotal role to play in combating the evolution of infectious disease, in understanding the emergence and spread of antibiotic resistance, and in the application of population genetic tools to trace lineages of bioterrorism agents. To accomplish this mission, however, requires the coordination and communication between a diversity of scientists, government agencies, policy makers, medical doctors, epidemiologists and others.

There is no institution or funding agency dedicated to the consolidation, synthesis and dissemination of this broad sweep of evolutionarily relevant information. The goal of this document is to report the outcome of two workshops aimed at addressing the scientific and national needs for an evolutionary synthesis center and propose mechanisms to meet these needs. The National Center for Ecological Analysis and Synthesis (NCEAS) provides a successful model for addressing the need for synthesis. NCEAS has implemented a successful scientific/social mechanism, the working group, which brings together scientists who collaborate to produce synthesis of ecological knowledge to address broad scientific and policy questions. A center for evolutionary synthesis modeled on NCEAS would serve first the needs of the evolutionary community by providing mechanisms to foster synthetic, collaborative, cross-disciplinary studies. The center would also play a pivotal role in the further unification of the biological sciences as it draws together knowledge from disparate biological fields to increase our general understanding of biological design and function. Finally, the center would play a critical role in organizing and synthesizing evolutionary knowledge that will inform policy makers, government agencies, educators and society, for instance in the fields of infectious disease, drug design, biological responses to global warming, biodefense and bioremediation.

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Introduction

The need for evolutionary synthesis

Evolutionary Biology has undergone a dramatic expansion in the past two decades. Evolution has grown from a sub-field of biology to an expansive and overarching discipline that now informs almost every aspect of the biological sciences. Evolution has long served to unify the study of biology, but it has now acquired a more central role. Philosophers of science recognize the principle of evolution by natural selection as the primary, perhaps the only, “natural law” peculiar to biology. Today, evolution informs and directs data acquisition, analysis and interpretation in all of the life sciences.

This transformation comes in part from the explosion of raw data, from sources as far ranging as genome sequences, functional and physiological genomics, ecological genomics, large-scale ecosystem studies, long-term behavioral studies, and phylogenetics. Such data and metadata can only be interpreted using advanced mathematical and statistical approaches built on evolutionary concepts and depends on highly developed database management and analysis tools. Whether we seek to understand the emergence of new diseases, develop new more effective plant cultivars, design novel therapeutic agents and antimicrobials, or account for the content and organization of newly sequenced genomes, we are using a comparative, evolutionary approach. We now incorporate phylogenetic methods in studies of microbial community structure, paternity and genealogy estimates in long-term behavioral studies, and comparative genomics in developmental studies. As formerly disparate fields of biological research converge, evolutionary biology is providing the common language.

Evolutionary biology is poised to serve as the focal point for the synthesis and interpretation of these massive and growing data sets. Even more compelling, it is the only field in the biological sciences capable of providing a unifying framework for fields as far ranging as rational drug design, developmental biology, cell biology, behavior, morphology, physiology, genetics, ecology, phylogenetics, and organismal biology. Progress is currently lagging in synthetic research even as the databases explode with information. The evolutionary biology community clearly sees the need for such synthetic research. There has been a virtual explosion of workshops focused on developing mechanisms to foster collaborative, cross-disciplinary, synthetic endeavors (for example, Tree of Life Workshops, EvoDevo meets the Tree of Life Workshop, Microbial Ecology and Genomics Workshop, Evolution, Science, and Society Workshops). However, there is no institution or funding agency dedicated to the consolidation, synthesis and dissemination of this broad sweep of evolutionarily relevant information.

The Evolutionary Synthesis Center Workshops I & II Goals

The NSF funded two workshops to address the need for an evolutionary synthesis center and to develop a plan of action to address this need. ESC workshop I convened at NSF headquarters in Arlington, Virginia from May 29th - June 1st, 2001. ESC Workshop II convened at Belmont Conference Center, Elkridge, Maryland from January 31st – February 3rd, 2002. The steering committee of the workshops was comprised of Margaret Riley, Yale University (Chair); Martin Feder, University of Chicago; Elizabeth Kellogg, University of Missouri; and David Maddison, University of Arizona. The 39 workshop participants were chosen to represent the following types of diversity:

- ***The breadth of organismal diversity*** - including microbes, plants and animals
- ***The breadth of evolutionary sub disciplines*** - including evolutionary morphology, evolutionary development, evolution of behavior, evolutionary ecology, population genetics, experimental evolution, molecular evolution, speciation, systematics, phylogenetics, paleontology, evolutionary theory, conservation genetics, comparative and functional genomics, artificial life, applied evolution, and bioinformatics
- ***The breadth of practical experiences*** – including research scientists, educators, experience running national scientific centers, participation in workshops to set research agendas, experience in technological and analytical tool development and database management, experience in running training programs, outreach programs, and educational programs
- ***The breadth of institutional types – including representatives from*** - universities, primarily undergraduate institutions, educational and outreach foundations, elected officers of relevant scientific societies, members of the national academy, national scientific centers, pharmaceutical and bioinformatics industries

ESC Workshop Participants

- Jeanne Altmann, Princeton University
- Charles Marshall, Harvard University
- Stephen Palumbi, Harvard University
- Gunter Wagner, Yale University
- Claiborne Stephens, Genaissance Pharmaceuticals
- Douglas Futuyma, SUNY, Stony Brook
- Jim Reichman, Univ. of California, Santa Barbara, Director of NCEAS
- Laura Katz, Smith College
- Scott Edwards, University of Washington
- Robin Bush, University of California, Irvine
- Susan Mazer, University of California, Santa Barbara
- Alison Withey, San Diego Supercomputer Center
- Emilia Martins, Indiana University
- Jennifer Wernegreen, MBL, Woods Hole
- David Hillis, University of Texas
- Robert Dorit, Smith College
- Nancy Moran, University of Arizona
- Spencer Muse, North Carolina State University
- Better Korber, Los Alamos National Laboratory
- David Stockwell, San Diego Supercomputer Center
- Ruth Shaw, University of Minnesota
- Geeta Bharatan, SUNY, Stony Brook
- Michael Lynch, Indiana University
- Ward Watt, Stanford University
- Mark Schildhauer, NCEAS
- David Jablonski, University of Chicago
- Tandy Warnow, University of Texas
- Gary Olsen, University of Illinois
- Hillol Kargupta, University of Maryland
- Billie Swalla, University of Washington

- Claudia Neuhauser, University of Minnesota
- Robert Feldman, Molecular Dynamics
- David Maddison, University of Arizona
- Elizabeth Kellogg, University of Missouri
- Martin Feder, University of Chicago
- Margaret Riley, Yale University
- Peter Midford, University of Arizona, rapporteur
- Brian Bettencourt, Pennsylvania State University, rapporteur
- Janet Barber, University of Missouri, rapporteur
- Scott Rifkin, Yale University, rapporteur

Four graduate student and postdoctoral fellows served as rapporteurs. The full list of attendees encompassed a broad representation of all stages of academic development, minority representation, nearly equal gender representation, and industry, government and academic representation.

ESC Workshop Agenda

The workshop participants were charged with addressing the following topics in plenary sessions, focused working groups and focused writing sessions:

- The mission of the ESC,
- The structure, administration, and facilities of the ESC,
- The mode of implementation of the ESC.

The goal of the two workshops was to discuss each topic and prepare a document for the National Science Foundation that will inform the NSF about the perceived and real needs for an evolutionary synthesis center and provide a detailed model of how such a center might be created.

ESC Workshop Report and Dissemination

The goal of these workshops is to develop a report for NSF that specifies the scientific and national needs that demand an evolutionary synthesis center. To succeed, this report must receive wide community support and describe a Center with which the evolutionary biology community will want to proceed, which means being sensitive to the aims and concerns of the entire evolution community. The steering committee was charged with preparation of a draft report summarizing the outcome of the two ESC workshops. This draft report was disseminated to the evolutionary community at large over the summer of 2002. Input, suggestions and modifications were solicited and incorporated into this final version.

Two modes of dissemination of the workshop draft report were employed.

Informing relevant scientific societies: The ESC workshop participants informed the most relevant scientific societies about the ESC initiative at annual meetings during 2002.

The following societies were contacted: American Society of Naturalists, Animal Behavior Society, Ecological Society of America, Genetics Society of America, Paleontological Society, Society for Vertebrate Paleontology, Society for Molecular Biology and Evolution, Society of Systematic Biologists, American Institute of Biological Sciences, Society for the Study of Evolution, European Society of Evolution Biology, Human Biology Society, Society for Integrative and Comparative Biology,

International Congress of Systematic and Evolutionary Biology and HIV Evolution and Dynamics Society.

- ***Informing the evolutionary biology community at large:*** An announcement regarding the ESC workshops, web site and draft report was made in the journal *Evolution* in late spring 2002. In addition, an announcement was sent to appropriate email list servers, including the evolution directory. A web site (www.esc.eeb.yale) provided a rough draft of this report and solicited comments.

The evolutionary biology community had the opportunity during the spring and summer of 2002 to view this draft report and offer suggestions and comments. The steering committee incorporated this input in the production of a final report for NSF.

The Scientific and National Need for an Evolutionary Synthesis Center

Why is synthesis needed?

Evolutionary biology has been spectacularly successful in providing a unified basis for biological research. Together with genetics and cell biology, evolutionary biology is essential for the understanding of every biological phenomenon, from the structure and variation of molecules to the organization and evolution of behavior and cognition. This spectacular success, however, poses a challenge: evolutionary knowledge is now so immense and diverse that individual scientists can comprehend only a small part of it. Without enhancing opportunities for scientists from disparate areas to work together on specific problems, the integrative power of evolutionary thinking and research is in jeopardy. Further, the efficiency of such interactions will be enhanced by providing a central structure for organizing the vast amount of existing and emerging data relevant for comparative questions. A Center for Evolutionary Synthesis, properly organized and funded, will enable the biological community to regain access to the full potential of evolutionary biology. Below we diagnose the causes of the current fragmentation and plan an Evolutionary Synthesis Center that can consolidate the field.

Evolutionary mechanisms proceed at many levels of biological organization, and include:

- Molecular processes that generate the genetic variation on which evolutionary change is based,
- Developmental and physiological processes that translate the genetic variation into genetic and phenotypic differences among individuals,
- Population processes that sort and select among the existing genetic variation,
- Genealogical processes that generate biodiversity, and
- Ecological feedbacks that influence the persistence of populations and species in the biosphere.

As a consequence, cutting-edge evolutionary research must operate at multiple levels of organization, each with its own research methodologies and concepts. For example, the sub disciplines of molecular evolution, quantitative genetics, evolutionary physiology, and evolutionary developmental biology are each highly specialized, requiring specialized training and expertise. Consequently, the community of evolutionary biologists, although not large in absolute numbers, finds itself organized in an increasing number of specialized scientific societies and publishing in an increasing number of specialized journals. The result is a highly dispersed distribution of biological knowledge. While the rise of new primary concepts will always depend on the insight of individual minds, the mass of available information and the diversity of research technologies now defy mastery by single individuals, no matter how talented. The international nature of modern evolutionary research, moreover, exacerbates this fragmentation. The scientific community thus needs a communal response to the challenge of its own success.

Evolutionary processes underlie many problems of both national and international concern. The general public has growing awareness, for example, of the threat to public health caused by evolution of antibiotic-resistant pathogens in our hospitals. The scientific community has long understood the mechanisms by which resistance evolves in response to the over-prescription of antibiotics. Yet this problem continues to grow, with bacteria having recently evolved resistance to “the antibiotic of last resort”, vancomycin. Clearly, understanding the process by which resistance evolves has failed to produce effective strategies to prevent resistance evolution by pathogens. The reasons for this failure are many, and a solution will only result from a many-faceted, synthetic approach. Biologists must understand the role of economic, legal, and public policy decisions on the evolutionary process, and experts in those fields will have to understand the problem from the biological view as well. The Evolutionary Synthesis Center could provide exactly this type of integration, bringing experts from these disparate fields together. Face to face interaction is needed to define and clarify problems, and to formulate solutions.

The problem of antibiotic resistance is not unique. Additional problems of national concern that require similar cooperation among evolutionary biologists, ecologists, economists, physicians, public health and government policy makers include:

- Biodefense,
- Evolution of infectious disease,
- Pesticide and herbicide resistance,
- Spread and evolution of genetically modified organisms,
- Spread and evolution of microbes through xenotransplantation,
- Evolutionary response of organisms to global warming,
- Bio-prospecting,
- Invasive species,
- Cancer.

Why A Synthesis Center?

Is a center the best way to achieve synthesis?

Evolutionary synthesis of the scope envisioned above will require the sustained and intense interaction of diverse experts drawn from the breadth of evolutionary biology as well as relevant areas of the remainder of the life sciences, medicine, the physical, quantitative and information sciences, agriculture, the social sciences, and the humanities. The concept of the “working group”, which brings together a moderate number of diversely experienced scientists to contemplate a specific challenge for synthesis, provides a flexible mechanism for fostering synthesis while avoiding limiting narrowness of viewpoint. Moreover, to achieve their goals, such experts will require ongoing and ready access to the raw information and meta-information to be synthesized.

Even with advances in electronic communications, there is still no substitute for physical presence in achieving the focused, high-intensity interaction that synthesis requires. Pragmatically, achieving this interaction is in part a matter of isolating the participants from the distractions of business as usual, part facilitating this interaction by physical proximity, part sustaining the interaction by keeping the participants together, and part

enabling the interaction by providing simple tools for accessing voluminous and complex databases. In other words, evolutionary synthesis of the scope envisioned above requires a physical center at which the synthesizers can assemble and interact.

If the requirement for a physical center for evolutionary synthesis is so obvious, why does not one already exist? In recent decades, institutional structures, both academic and funding, in biology have tended toward fragmentation of the field into specialized sub-disciplines, partly in recognition of the increasing challenges and need for greater technical expertise. Typically, basic biology is separate from medicine, the biological and medical sciences separate from the physical sciences, the natural sciences separate from the social sciences, and the sciences separate from the humanities. Funders of knowledge acquisition and analysis, both governmental and non-governmental, largely followed suit, although most are now recognizing the need for synthesis to balance specialization (e.g., the present effort to articulate the need for an Evolutionary Synthesis Center, NSF's Biocomplexity Initiative). Thus, neither academic, governmental, nor other institutions have developed feasible centers for coalescence, interaction, and integration on the scale and scope required for the level of synthesis needed.

Thus, we propose that a national need exists for a center for evolutionary synthesis. A center for evolutionary synthesis will lead to otherwise impossible advances both in our fundamental understanding of evolutionary processes and in resolving major practical problems of national significance. Moreover, as outlined below, this center would develop key tools for meta-information databasing and analysis with broad utility beyond evolutionary synthesis, and be autocatalytic in generating diverse human resources and a scientific culture committed to evolutionary synthesis. No structure that will fulfill this need currently exists.

What Will Synthesis Achieve?

A proven concept rather than wishful thinking

A synthetic center of this magnitude can readily be envisioned, but can it actually be achieved? We ourselves might be skeptical except for a counterpart center that already exists, the National Center for Ecological Analysis and Synthesis in Santa Barbara. This NSF-funded Center has successfully implemented a novel scientific-social structure; the "working group" that actually produces the kind of interaction that evolutionary synthesis will require and has been credited with a revolution in the scientific interactions of ecologists. To date, NCEAS working groups have produced more than 450 publications, many appearing in journals such as *Science* and *Nature*, have involved more than 2,300 of the scientists in that field, and have trained the next generation of academic leadership in ecology. Moreover, NCEAS has shown that working groups can in real time be provided with access to mega databases and information specialists, and has proven a form of management that is flexible but achieves an extremely high quality of scientific product.

Biological processes occurring at different temporal and spatial scales and at distinct ecological levels do not operate in isolation. Ecological and evolutionary processes occurring at one level often directly or indirectly influence those observed at other levels. To illustrate, a synthetic, multi-level study of the evolution of any behavioral or morphological trait (e.g., lifespan, seed size, body mass, mate choice, disease resistance, herbicide resistance, etc.) — and the causal mechanisms underlying such evolution — might include:

- Functional genomicists (to identify genes associated with particular phenotypes),
- Physiologists (to characterize the physiological attributes of alternative genotypes and phenotypes),
- Evolutionary ecologists (to estimate the strength of natural selection and to predict the evolutionary response to this selection),
- Quantitative geneticists (to evaluate genetic versus environmental determinants of a phenotype),
- Behavioral ecologists (to identify behaviors associated with alternative phenotypes)
- Community ecologists (to determine whether population-level phenotypic changes affect interspecific interactions),
- Systematists (to characterize the diversity of life),
- Comparative biologists (to determine whether these traits coevolve with other traits or affect higher level patterns of diversification),
- Paleoecologists (to reconstruct historical events associated with long-term morphological evolution), and
- Statisticians or mathematicians (to develop the required analytical tools).

New insights into evolutionary processes and novel applications of evolutionary theory can continue to be generated by developing new collaborations with researchers in disciplines outside of evolutionary biology. Advances of this type have already been observed as computer scientists have borrowed from evolutionary theory to develop genetic algorithms used for aircraft design, robot design, and other feats of engineering. We anticipate other fruitful interactions with scientists in the fields of medicine, agriculture, information technology, ecology, biotechnology, economics, public policy, philosophy, geophysical science, and astronomy.

Synthesis-enabled science

A number of directions and approaches to pure research will be enabled by a Center devoted to evolutionary synthesis. Such directions include projects whose scale (sheer size and number of levels of bio-organization spanned) will surpass typical single PI, single level research in evolutionary biology. The Center will enable a new type of evolutionary inquiry that will come about only through collaborations of diverse scientists and policy makers. Such research directions include, but are not limited to:

- **Whole-genome evolutionary analysis:** The analysis of megabase-scale DNA sequences across diverse taxa and clades will provide fundamental insights into genome evolution. The comparative analysis of multigene families, isochores, repetitive sequences and coding sequences will be enhanced through understanding of the genomic contexts in which each occurs and their interrelationships.

- **Consequences of genetic and ecological interactions at multiple scales:** Synthesis will permit tests of the ability of interactions at one level of biological organization to impact variation and interactions at other levels. For example, the consequences of epistasis among genes for genotype-environmental covariances and the subsequent effects on social, ecological and interspecific interactions can be explored.
- **Major features of evolution:** Synthesis will permit an exploration of the connections between global ecological change and complexity of biological organization in paleontological time. The major transitions in evolution, such as the origin of life, evolution of multicellularity, and symbioses in cellular evolution can be linked to environmental changes, the evolution of geochemical cycles and interactions among life forms.
- **Outer limits of evolvability:** The constraints and limits placed on evolutionary change by the structure of genomes, rules of inheritance and variation, and interactions at different hierarchical levels can be defined and tested. The possibility of predicting evolutionary change can be evaluated by rigorous synthesis of perspectives in quantitative and evolutionary genetics, and correlations with environmental change.

Spin-offs of synthesis for the worldwide community of evolutionary biologists

As a consequence of its research and outreach activities, the Center will provide a number of additional tools and resources for the global evolutionary biology community that are not yet in place. The Center will provide and facilitate:

- Unprecedented databasing capabilities that will permit the manipulation and handling of multiple databases of diverse types,
- Partnerships among diverse societies and scientists, and serve as a meeting place for interactions among these groups,
- Added value to a multitude of databases, specimen collections and research programs funded by NSF and other organizations - the synthesis of diverse approaches and data will enhance the value of the diverse array of projects already being funded, ongoing, or completed,
- A new set of statistical tools and models to better deal with the linkages between data types and structures that have not hitherto been considered simultaneously,
- New tools for functional genomics and the identification of genes of importance to biomedicine and agriculture through evolutionary analysis. Comparative genomics informed by evolutionary logic and phylogenetics will provide powerful new ways to discover genes and their functions.

Evolutionary synthesis and national needs

Not only would an Evolutionary Synthesis Center achieve breakthroughs in understanding evolution, it would likely pave the way for major advances on significant problems of national concerns to which evolutionary biology is relevant. These include:

- **Biodefense.** The recent tragedies resulting from anthrax bioterrorism have illustrated significant weaknesses in our nations abilities to detect, trace, and respond to biological threats. The evolutionary community is poised to contribute significantly to this immediate national need with their expertise in population genetics, microbial diversity and evolution. A successful plan for combating

bioterrorism will require tools for delineating pathogen population structure, molecular methods for lineage tracing or clone detection, and population genetic theory for predicting responses to vaccines or antibiotics.

- ***Evolution of infectious disease.*** The rapid evolution of HIV has delayed effective vaccine development. In influenza, rapid evolution necessitates continual reformulation of the vaccine. Our lack of effective vaccines against more slowly evolving microbes such as malaria and chlamydia clearly come from our lack of understanding of how they have co-evolved to evade the immune systems of their hosts.
- ***Pesticide/herbicide resistance.*** Pesticide and herbicide use, and abuse, has led to the evolution of resistance in target organisms. As with antibiotic resistance, this problem arose in part through our lack of understanding of the evolutionary biology of these systems. Economics, unfortunately, has played a major role in the continuing escalation of these problems. This is certainly an area in which the ESC could make a major contribution.
- ***Spread and evolution of genetically modified organisms.*** We now have the technical ability to insert foreign genes into plants and animals. There is much concern as to the safety of these systems. What if the antibiotic resistance genes used as markers in transgenic plants evolve in a manner allowing them to spread widely? Plants have recently been altered to produce proteins native to the hepatitis C virus. These plants are in essence edible vaccines. What will happen if these genes recombine with other human viruses inside our bodies, or otherwise evolve within us into something unexpected and unwelcome?
- ***Spread and evolution of microbes through xenotransplantation.*** Transfer of organs between species has been proposed to aid humans experiencing organ failure. The potential for introducing novel pathogens into humans through xenotransplantation is a serious concern, particularly because these patients are immunosuppressed, and thus allow little restriction to the growth and evolution of microbes. Although organ transplantation was not involved in the transfer of HIV from primates to humans, the devastating spread of this disease illustrates the potential dangers from this source. Using tissue from less closely related animals is no guarantee of safety, as recent studies have shown that porcine endogenous retroviruses can infect and replicate within human cells in culture.
- ***Evolutionary response of organisms to global warming.*** Predictions of biome change due to global warming typically focus on the replacement or loss of species in particular geographic areas. However, organisms will not simply be moving to new locales. Some species will stay put and adapt to the new climate. Species that migrate will adapt to both a new physical and biotic environment. Neglecting the role of adaptive responses to climate change is clearly a mistake.
- ***Bio-prospecting.*** Organisms with medicinal or other economic potential may have close relatives with similar usefulness. Phylogenetics is the means used to determine relatedness, and thus the potential economic loss we may incur with the current decrease of biodiversity due to habitat destruction. A synthetic approach to this problem is especially needed in the tropics, where it greatly impacts the politics of land use and conservation.

- ***Invasive Species.*** New and invasive species not only undergo rapid evolution in response to their new physical and biotic environments, but the organisms they impact in their new environments will adapt to the invaders as well. These unplanned experiments in evolution have shown we had little ability to predict the outcome of planned introductions, and thus show how badly a synthetic approach is needed before performing planned introductions, such as introducing microbes for biological control.
- ***Cancer.*** Evolution plays a role in both the origin and treatment of cancer. Natural selection favors mutations, which increase the growth rate and longevity of cell lines, and similarly favors mutations that allow the cells to resist chemotherapy. Cancer has received very little attention from the evolution community and thus the ESC might provide groundbreaking opportunities to make progress in this field.

There are many stakeholder communities involved in the creation of an Evolutionary Synthesis Center and experience shows that NSF sponsorship of such programs can revolutionize and unite a field.

The ESC Mission and Structure

ESC Mission Statement

The ESC will employ an evolutionary framework to advance and integrate biological, physical, mathematical, computational, and social information into a synthetic view of biocomplexity.

We envision an interdisciplinary center that brings together scientists to focus on wide-ranging evolutionary questions that cut across diverse fields. The center will be constructed on a model similar to NCEAS, through focused working groups, post-doctoral researchers, visiting scientists- and writers-in-residence, partners, and graduate and undergraduate interns.

To meet its goals, the ESC must be maximally flexible and responsive to proposals produced by scientists and educators from diverse segments of the evolutionary community. Specific research goals should not be defined in advance. Below is a list of some of the roles the ESC might fill. This list is certainly not exhaustive, but illustrates some examples of projects that would be enhanced by a center and/or would be impossible without one.

- ***Linking disparate data sets:*** Complex data sets are already available for different aspects of the same biological community. Synthesis of these pre-existing data sets would facilitate answering crucial questions central to biology. For example, taxonomic diversity and composition of oceanic plankton communities are important to interpretation of the fossil record and past climates. Comparison of these records to current data sets on ocean environment, productivity and weather will fine-tune efforts to understand the earth's climatic history and predict future climate change.

- ***Integrating data to solve conceptual problems:*** Exploring existing data sets from new perspectives and with new tools can advance many evolutionary problems. By providing a framework for novel analysis of existing data, the ESC could define the state-of-the-art for many ongoing research questions. For example, connection of GenBank and other NCBI databases to a database of phylogenetic trees via novel computational tools would allow investigation of the occurrence and evolution of duplicated genes and patterns of protein evolution.
- ***Summarizing existing information:*** A wealth of biological information is sequestered in obscure journals, in unusual formats, and in narrowly disseminated sources such as theses. The Center will provide a place in which scientists can mine the existing data resources and have support staff that will help with data entry and translating data into unified formats so that they can be adequately summarized. For example, museum records of species occurrences could be used to understand community diversity in space and time.
- ***Analytical and statistical tool development:*** For many biological problems, necessary analytical tools are not available. Different algorithms for analyzing evolutionary data arise from many different sources. Often, these are inadvertently “customized”, but with a modest amount of help from skilled computer scientists, could be broadened and made available to a much wider community. For example, phylogeneticists currently using likelihood approaches could be connected to molecular evolutionists, mathematicians and computer scientists to develop more robust maximum likelihood methods for a broader community of users.
- ***IT tool development:*** For many evolutionary biologists there is a need to connect disparate databases. Tools to enable novel connections will be developed at the Center by direct collaboration between the evolutionary biologists and information technologists. For example, IT scientists could develop tools to link phylogeneticists with data from museums, genomes, etc. and with taxon-centered communities. This would result in web sites such as FlyBase and Gene Ontology.
- ***Think tank:*** Many fields in evolutionary biology have datasets that can be applied to globally relevant research questions. For example, genome scientists studying gene expression and ecological/evolutionary diversity could be connected to entomologists, evolutionary ecologists and atmospheric scientists to plan for large-scale integrative investigations of insect physiology in relation to climate.
- ***Bringing theorists & empiricists together:*** Many theoretical problems would benefit from empirical testing. Conversely, theory can guide collection and interpretation of novel datasets. For example, IT specialists could collaborate with plant genome scientists to develop connections for the study of comparative evolutionary development. This could result in theory and analytical tools for comparing genome maps, microarray data, etc.
- ***Training students & postdocs in synthetic approaches:*** IT post doctoral fellows could be assigned to working groups to develop novel database analysis tools, etc. For example, IT postdoctoral fellows could be connected with behavioral scientists to develop novel database designs for handling behavioral data.

- ***Juxtaposing scientists who might not normally interact:*** Some of the most exciting science comes out of interactions between scientists who do not normally collaborate. For example, a Center workshop could connect chemists, microbiologists, geologists, phylogeneticists, astronomers, biochemists, enzymologists and industrial biotechnologists in the study of microbial communities. Such a collaborative effort will aid in our understanding of the biology of organisms of extreme environment, their history and likely future importance.
- ***Developing effective tools and resources for evolution education:*** The capabilities of professional educators, science writers and research scientists are needed to develop effective evolution education resources. This effort might involve the design of evolution lab exercises, lessons on how evolution impacts society, and the role evolution plays in understanding our place in nature.
- ***Supporting investigations of emerging fields:*** The working group model would provide opportunities for activities aimed at enabling research in emerging areas of evolutionary biology. Such activities are difficult to coordinate with existing models of support.

ESC Structure and Facilities

We envision a structure that resembles, in part, that found at NCEAS. The Center will be housed off-campus but with strong connections to one or more universities. The Center will require office and meeting space for a collection of working groups, postdoctoral fellows, student interns, scientists- and writers-in-residence, and support staff. In addition, the Center will quickly attract a variety of partners from industry, government agencies and national centers. Figure 1 provides a conceptual model of the proposed ESC structure.

ESC Mechanisms of Synthesis and Outreach

Evolutionary Synthesis Mechanisms

The objectives of the Center are to provide a forum for informal and formal interaction and collaboration, especially among interdisciplinary groups from diverse backgrounds. The Center will be built around the successful NCEAS model. The Center would sponsor:

- ***Working groups*** – composed of researchers gathering to solve a problem or map new directions
- ***Post-doctoral fellowships*** – on-site fellowships to develop and pursue novel synthetic approaches
- ***Sabbaticals*** – fellows-in-residence for extended periods to allow a sustained and intensive effort in synthetic research and outreach efforts

Graduate and undergraduate student interns – on-site and off-site interns attached to particular working groups and involved in data and metadata entry and analysis, synthesis, outreach and education efforts.

Partners – Fellows funded by industry, government agencies and other National Centers engaged in extended interaction with evolutionary synthesis efforts may be connected to existing working groups or work independently.

Figure 1. Evolutionary Synthesis Center Structure and Facilities

The Center will maintain a mix of these, as well as explore other potential mechanisms to enable synthesis. The Center should be an exciting locus that enables communication, collaboration and intellectual exchange among researchers from a diversity of disciplines.

The ESC will support projects that are synthetic, interdisciplinary, in emerging fields, risky/exploratory, and under-represented fields, fields at the margins of evolutionary biology, with educational values, from investigators representing diversity in gender, taxon, approach, philosophy, age, rank, and type of institution. Examples of the types of projects that would be supported by the Center are provided above (see page 16).

Evolutionary Outreach Mechanisms

The Center will serve as the primary source for dissemination of evolutionary synthesis information and products both nationally and internationally. It will play a critical role in enabling efforts to create and disseminate evolutionary synthesis information and products through writers-in-residence, journalism interns, policy postdoctoral fellowships and outreach-oriented working groups. It is critical that the Outreach and Synthesis goals be integrated at the Center. Evolutionary biology is directly relevant to many national and societal concerns (such as biodefense, creationism versus evolution debates, science education, antibiotic resistance evolution, the biological impact of global warming, etc.). These needs should be represented in the working groups either through outreach specialists participating in particular working groups or working groups devoted to specific outreach topics. The Center will disseminate evolutionary synthesis information to the government, community, industry, foundations, education community and public and other relevant forums.

Evolutionary Synthesis Enabling and Support

Administrative Support

A Director and Advisory Board will administer the ESC. The choice and mechanisms of choice of the Director and Board are critical, as they will set the tone for the Center. Following the NCEAS model, in order to attract a pool of qualified applicants, the Center Director is provided a tenure appointment at an affiliated University and has no set term limit. The Director is responsible for the day-to-day administration of the Center and works closely with the Advisory Board regarding all funding decisions.

The Advisory Board is composed of 15 to 20 individuals, with rotating two to three year terms. Mechanisms for determining board membership might involve community nominations and voting, Board Member nominations and board voting, etc. The Board members should be inclusive of disciplines, under-represented groups, and different career stages. These individuals will represent the diversity of institutions including universities, primary undergraduate institutions, industry, educational agencies, and other national scientific centers as appropriate.

One of the primary missions of the Board is to provide a flexible and speedy funding process that can meet the synthesis and outreach needs of the community. A set of principles that captures some of the flexibility and quality assurance used by NCEAS will guide the Director and Board in their funding process. These principles will ensure that the funding process for all programs at the Center be transparent. Proposals will be considered through a formal in-house review system that provides written feedback to the investigators.

Analytical, Mathematical and Computational Support

The primary functions of the analytical, mathematical and computational support group are to enable, support and inspire the working groups, fellows, partners, and other participants at the Center. This enabling and support group will play a critical role in

ensuring the success of the Center and lengthy consideration of the extensive computational, software and analytical tools that this support group must provide and maintain is essential. To meet the diverse computation and analytical needs of the Center, this support group will provide and maintain the central computational system, appropriate hardware (laptops), connections (email, web, etc.) and software (data entry, database management and analysis, etc.). As common needs for analysis and software development are realized, the support group will engage in development of raw analysis software, database entries and databases. They will develop new tools for databases and new methods of synthesis of heterogeneous data. They will help fellows, partners and working groups to deliver open source, general, interoperable and compatible databases and software.

The capabilities needed by the ESC and enabled by this support unit include:

- Assembly of information from diverse sources into common and readily manipulated format;
- Structuring, manipulation, and analysis within that format;
- Eventual redistribution of the restructured, reformatted data, and results, derived from them, as widely as may be appropriate.
- Facilitating these tasks in themselves may result in a variety of new tools.

Some member of this support group will need to possess considerable expertise as a data reference librarian and retrieval specialist in order to facilitate efficient knowledge sharing among working groups, between working groups and the Director, and most especially in providing or even translating results of the Center's activities for dissemination by the Outreach Support Staff.

Outreach Support

The primary function of the Outreach support staff is to enable ESC outreach efforts. Outreach goals have been woven into the central mission of the Center and much of the outreach activities will occur within existing working groups and in outreach-specific working groups as well as through interns (policy, education, etc). However, there is a critical need for professionals to take charge of the dissemination of this outreach information to the appropriate audience.

There are three primary outreach functions that require devoted professionals.

- **Education information flow:** There are numerous agencies, centers and foundations devoted to science education (such as NCSE). The ESC will not attempt to duplicate their efforts. However, the Center will play a central role in the dissemination of evolutionary synthesis information and products to the appropriate institutions. The education audience is vast and diverse and this mission will require a full-time, professional education outreach facilitator.
- **Public relations and press interface:** An equally critical need for evolution education is directed at the media and press. A professional in public relations is required to take on the enormous task of informing the media, press, and other news agencies of evolutionary-relevant information. The national need for an informed society is critical. The Center will play a primary role in enabling public education about evolutionary information and the role of evolution in

addressing national needs. The World Wide Web plays an increasing prominent role in serving as a primary source of information. The Center website would serve as a passive form of evolutionary information communication targeted at the evolution community, life sciences community, educators, news media, etc. A web master is required to develop and maintain this constantly increasing stream of evolutionary information.

- **Industry, institution and foundation liaisons and development:** The long term success of the Center requires engagement of non-governmental resources. A program, centered in the working group and fellows programs, that involves partners from industry, partners from other National Centers and the like will ensure a continuous influx of evolutionary information into these non government channels and establish ties that may lead to additional mechanisms to fund Center activities.